

Covid19 – A Mathematical modelling of a PSEUDO-GAUSSIAN

Contour

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Microbial Kinetics, Exponential Phase , Biopolymers , Root Mean End to End Separation , Radius of gyration , Hydrodynamic Modelling , Gaussian Probability , Superimposition

Most of the Microbial growth kinetics (including Bacterial & Viral) follows four stages namely ,
1. LAG PHASE 2. **LOG PHASE (EXPONENTIAL PHASE** For Covid19) 3. STATIC or STATIONARY PHASE
4. DECLINING PHASE. The second phase is taken into consideration for mathematical modelling . Under this present pandemic situation of Covid19 - A Virulent microbes where exponential phase is much higher and uncontrollable. Only prolonged lockdown period will make the sharp exponential phase to flat one ..

The Exponential Phase Kinetics can be described as **It is an EXPONENTIAL F(X) of the growth curve .**

$$Ct = C_0 * \text{EXP} (- K * t) \dots\dots(1)$$

[Where C_0 = Initial Viral count & K = 1st order growth const depending on the nature of covid 19 & t = time of growth / spreading of Virus]

The data of some BIOPOLYMERS (Including Virus like Covid19) (N =Number of Monomers vs R_{rms} = An Important Statistical Properties ROOT MEAN SQ END TO END SEPARATION is a F(X) of RADIUS OF GYRATION (R_g)) are analysed a BEST FIT STATISTICA shows an EXP fit .The output of the CURVE is expressed as :

$$N = 267.136 * \exp (0.042 * R_{rms}) \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

N = Number of covid19 Units , R_g and R_{rms} are the Statistical Parameters which includes the quick spreading of Covid19 infection .

Now for Covid19 the most interesting phenomenon is only exponential phase is significant the Stationary Phase may be considered as also a sharp decline to be superimposed just like Gaussian Distribution and it may be termed as **Pseudo-exponential Contour** .

The Gaussian distribution the General mathematical expression of Probability Distribution can be expressed as $P (x) = A \exp (- B * x ^ 2) \dots\dots\dots(3)$

For one dimension ranging from - infinity to + infinity the Average distribution is ZERO .

For two /three dimension the expression includes dimension factor .

To find best fit analysis through Regression method the Gaussian fit is one of the useful one for Hydrodynamic Modelling of Covid19 ie the flow of virus inside Blood .

The above three equations (1, 2 & 3) can be solved to combine the mathematical model for a Pseudo – Gaussian distribution curve – where the value of A can be compared with 267.136 and B can be compared to 0.042 and the composite equation become :

$$P(N, x) = 267.136 * \exp(-0.042 * Rrms^2) \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

This equation (4) meets the criteria of Pseudo- Gaussian Contour (ie a hypothetical

Super imposition of microbial growth kinetics and Gaussian distribution) referred below :

REFERENCE :

1. **Datta J , MICROBIAL GROWTH KINETICS : A MATHEMATICAL REVIEW (SPECIAL ADDENDUM - COVID19) (figshare.com) , May , 2020 .**
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